

MEDICAL SCIENCES

VITAMIN D AND REUMATOID ARTRITIS

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Abstract

Vitamin D has been reported to influence physiological systems that extend far beyond its established functions in calcium and bone homeostasis. Prominent amongst these are the potent immunomodulatory effects of the active form of vitamin D, 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ (1,25-(OH)₂D₃). The nuclear vitamin D receptor (VDR) for 1,25-(OH)₂D₃ is expressed by many cells within the immune system and resulting effects include modulation of T cell phenotype to suppress pro-inflammatory Th1 and Th17 CD4+ T cells and promote tolerogenic regulatory T cells. In addition, antigen-presenting cells have been shown to express the enzyme 1 α -hydroxylase that converts precursor 25-hydroxyvitamin D₃ (25-OHD₃) to 1,25-(OH)₂D₃, so that immune microenvironments are able to both activate and respond to vitamin D. As a consequence of this local, intracrine, system, immune responses may vary according to the availability of 25-OHD₃, and vitamin D deficiency has been linked to various autoimmune disorders including rheumatoid arthritis (RA). The aim of this review is to explore the immune activities of vitamin D that impact autoimmune disease, with specific reference to RA. As well as outlining the mechanisms linking vitamin D with autoimmune disease, the review will also describe the different studies that have linked vitamin D status to RA, and the current supplementation studies that have explored the potential benefits of vitamin D for prevention or treatment of RA. The overall aim of the review is to provide a fresh perspective on the potential role of vitamin D in RA pathogenesis and treatment.

Keywords: vitamin D, Vitamin D receptor, Autoimmune disease, Rheumatoid arthritis, Inflammation, T cell.

Introduction

Vitamin D is a secosteroid which can be obtained from the diet (in particular from oily fish, eggs, dairy products and fortified foods). Part of vitamin D is synthesised in the skin from the precursor molecule 7-dehydrocholesterol, which undergoes a series of UV light-mediated modifications to generate parental vitamin D₃ (1). Vitamin D was first recognised for its role in bone mineralisation and calcium regulation, with vitamin D deficiency associated with the bone disease rickets (2). More recently, vitamin D has been reported to exert many extraskeletal effects (3) with association studies linking vitamin D status to a broad range of human health issues. Prominent amongst these is the proposed role of vitamin D in the pathophysiology of autoimmune disease, including insulin-dependent type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1D) (4), autoimmune thyroid disease (5, 6), multiple sclerosis (MS), inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) (7), systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) (8) and rheumatoid arthritis (RA) (9). The underlying mechanisms by which vitamin D impacts autoimmune disease remain elusive, and it is still not clear whether vitamin D deficiency contributes to autoimmune disease pathogenesis or whether it is marker of disease progression and severity. In this article, we address these issues with specific reference to the role of

vitamin D in RA. We discuss the potential clinical significance, and the mechanisms of action of vitamin D in RA, and suggest areas where future research is needed.

Vitamin D and Immunity

The multi-modal innate immune system is the body's first line of defence against pathogens, comprising physical barriers (e.g. epithelium), chemical barriers (e.g. stomach acid), complement proteins and cellular responses such as those mediated by macrophage, DC and neutrophils. Vitamin D participates in several of these processes, including the maintenance of barrier function in the intestine, by regulating tight junctions (10) and intestinal epithelial cell apoptosis (11). However, to date, studies of vitamin D and innate immunity have predominantly explored its impact on antigen-presenting cells, such as macrophages and DC, which participate in the recognition of and response to pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) via pattern recognition receptors (PRR). DNA target sequences for 1,25-(OH)₂D₃-bound to VDR, referred to as vitamin D response elements (VDRE) have been found in multiple genes associated with PRR responses, including the antibacterial proteins NOD2, hepcidin antimicrobial protein (HAMP), cathelicidin, B-defensin 2 (DEFB4) and TREM-1. Toll-Like Receptors (TLRs) are an important group of PRR, and 1,25-(OH)₂D₃ has been

shown to downregulate TLR2 and TLR4 in monocytes, abrogating over-elaboration of TLR immune responses to PAMPs and damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs). In a separate study, methylation of the Vitamin D Receptor (VDR) gene and single-nucleotide polymorphisms in the VDR were also found to alter VDR-mediated TLR1/2 signalling in monocytes.

Vitamin D is also known to differentially regulate innate immune cell subsets, influencing cell maturation, metabolism and antigen presentation, alongside response to and production of cytokines and chemokines. Notably, mature DC express CYP27B1 but little VDR, whereas the converse is true for immature DC. This has led to the hypothesis that mature DC may in fact produce vitamin D locally on activation, which then acts on immature DC to modulate immune responses. The principal effect of 1,25-(OH)2D3 on DC is to suppress maturation markers such as CD80/CD86 and CD83, increase IL-10 production and decrease pro-inflammatory cytokines. In this way, 1,25(OH)2D3 promotes an immature, tolerogenic DC phenotype, thereby reducing antigen presentation to T cells.

Adaptive immune cells are also modulated directly by 1,25-(OH)2D3, with VDR being transiently expressed by developing thymocytes, and re-activation of VDR expression in peripheral T and B cells following immune challenge. 1,25-(OH)2D3 was initially thought to act primarily as a regulator of T and B cell proliferation, but is now known to play a more important role in regulating T cell phenotype. In particular, 1,25-(OH)2D3 has been shown to suppress inflammatory interleukin-17 expressing CD4+ T-helper (Th) cells (Th17) and Th1 cells, whilst promoting differentiation of Th2 cells and regulatory T cells (Treg). However, vitamin D may also promote some immune responses by enhancing effector T cell responses including CD8+ cytotoxic function, and other studies have reported a role for 1,25-(OH)2D3 in promoting T cell receptor (TCR) expression and T cell activation. Although less well studied, 1,25-(OH)2D3 has also been shown to modulate the function of other cytotoxic lymphocytes such as natural killer cells (NK), with apparent effects of NK cell activation. Likewise, effects of vitamin D have been described for natural killer T cells (NKT), and NKT cell development is lost in mice lacking the VDR gene. In contrast to the wide range of data on vitamin D and T cells, there is a scarcity of detailed studies for effects of 1,25-(OH)2D3 on B cells, which may include indirect effects via T cell modulation, and direct B cell effects on class switching, IL-10 production and CCR10 production.

Vitamin D and Rheumatoid Arthritis

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory/autoimmune arthritis characterised by synovitis of peripheral joints, with extra-articular manifestations. If untreated, unopposed inflammation leads to joint destruction, loss of function and disability, and RA is also associated with premature mortality secondary, at least in part, to the effects of chronic inflammation on cardiovascular health. Like other autoimmune diseases, there is growing interest in the role of vitamin D deficiency in the aetiopathogenesis of RA. RA is thought to be triggered by environmental factors, in patients with

an underlying genetic susceptibility leading to dysfunction of innate and adaptive immunity, tipping the balance in preference of autoimmunity over tolerance. Whilst smoking is well recognised as a strong environmental risk factor other potential factors include vitamin D.

Vitamin D Status and RA Disease Risk and Progress

In a recent meta-analysis and systematic review, Lin J et al. analysed 24 studies published prior to May 2015 whose focus was the relationship between serum 25-OHD3 and clinical/laboratory indices of RA disease activity. Over all, they reported an inverse relationship between serum 25-OHD3 and RA disease activity. However, they also identified important differences between patient subgroups, including a stronger inverse relationship between RA disease activity and serum 25-OHD3 in studies from developing countries, and in low-latitude climates. Since the publication of this meta-analysis, further studies have been conducted. Therefore, to establish a clearer picture of whether vitamin D levels are indeed significantly lower in RA, and are linked to disease activity. The search terms “vitamin D levels” and “rheumatoid arthritis” were used, and no restrictions on study date were applied. In addition, studies included in the meta-analysis (referenced above) were also included. The collected studies underline the significant heterogeneity between studies and their findings, making it difficult to determine a clear role for vitamin D deficiency in the onset, progression and/ or severity of RA. Studies to date have been conducted in over 20 countries, which invariably means that there will be confounding differences in environmental factors including sunlight exposure and diet, and genetic factors. Moreover, the overwhelming majority of the reported studies were observational or cross-sectional by design, and as such can only report on the association between RA disease and vitamin D, rather than a causal role.

RA is a heterogeneous disease, yet few studies have considered analysing RA subgroups based on antibody status, disease severity or duration. Where subgroups have been defined, this is often based on disease activity score 28 (DAS-28); a composite score that captures different subjective and objective measures of disease activity, hence the potential for skewing of results by one component. One study that did address this reported no correlation between vitamin D levels and DAS-28, with or without the inclusion of the patient global visual analogue scale score (Patient global VAS)—a scale for evaluating the patient’s overall perception of their RA activity. However, patient global VAS on its own did correlate with serum vitamin D levels. In 2015, Cooles et al. reported data showing the relationship between serum 25-OHD3 levels and various clinical parameters in early RA (median symptom duration 12 weeks, range 4–104 weeks). They found no clear association between 25-OHD3 and early RA, but in early osteoarthritis (OA) 25-OHD3 was inversely associated with global health visual analogue scale scores (GH-VAS). This suggests that OA, which commonly co-exists with RA, may act as a confounder in interpreting the relationship between vitamin D and RA. These

observations are intriguing, and need to be further explored to determine the role, if any, for vitamin D in pain and fatigue associated with RA.

Relatively few studies have assessed the impact of RA treatment regimens on the apparent inverse correlation between serum 25-OHD3 and RA disease activity. Treatment for RA is aimed at reducing disease activity, and therefore comparing serum 25-OHD3 levels with measures of disease activity after the initiation of treatment could mask prior effects of vitamin D deficiency on treatment naïve disease. Since the 1990s, an early and aggressive approach to the management of new RA has been widely used in order to maximise chances of inducing remission. Today, this strategy is fully integrated in clinical practice, but its application in the context of low vitamin D, and vitamin D replacement, for treatment naïve, newly diagnosed RA patients, is still unclear.

As well as clinical and biochemical differences in sub-groups of RA, there are also likely genetic differences which may influence the relative importance of vitamin D in the immunopathogenesis of disease. For example, Dennis et al. identified four distinct synovial tissue gene expression profiles in a cohort of RA patients. Although some of these differences in gene expression may be related to the patient's disease duration or treatment regimen, it seems unlikely that this sufficiently explains all the observed differences, and that distinctly different gene signatures may indeed characterise different subsets of RA. Accordingly, it seems plausible that vitamin D deficiency may play slightly different roles in the aetiopathogenesis and progression of disease in different groups of patients. Ultimately, the role of vitamin D in RA appears far too complex to be understood through simple observational methods.

To date, studies of RA disease and vitamin D have focused on the link between RA and serum levels of the main circulating form of vitamin D, 25-OHD3. However, 25OHD3 is an inactive precursor for 1,25-(OH)2D3 and therefore has limited functional relevance for immunomodulation. Consequently, there has been a revival of interest in the role of other vitamin D metabolites both in serum and disease-affected synovial fluid as potentially more informative markers for vitamin D function in RA. Research on this subject began more than 25 years ago with seminal studies of vitamin D metabolism in RA tissues. These reports indicated that concentrations of 25-OHD3 were significantly lower in synovial fluid relative to paired patient blood, but also revealed significant capacity for the generation of 1,25-(OH)2D3 by macrophages isolated from synovial fluid. In more recent studies, we have measured multiple vitamin D metabolites—the vitamin D 'metabome' in paired serum and synovial fluid from patients with established RA, reactive arthritis and healthy controls using the current gold standard for vitamin D analysis, liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC–MS/MS). These studies showed that for markers such as swollen joint count (SJC), synovial fluid levels of vitamin D metabolites correlated better with RA disease activity than their circulating serum counterparts.

Another area of contention for vitamin D and RA concerns the definition of vitamin D deficiency itself.

In the UK, the National Institute of Clinical Excellence (NICE) recommends diagnosis of vitamin D deficiency when serum 25-OHD3 is < 30 ng/mL, and states that for some people 30-50 ng/mL may be insufficient, citing recommendations from the national osteoporosis society guidelines. Hence, there appears to be an ambiguity around whether or not some patients need more vitamin D than others. Current NICE guidance does not define what constitutes adequate vitamin D status in patients of different ages, sex, ethnicities or disease states; for example, patients at risk of RA vs patients with established RA, or in other inflammatory diseases. To date, few studies have attempted to define what adequate supplementation means in RA. A cohort study published in 2012 observed that even supplementation 800-880 IU/day did not achieve adequate repletion of vitamin D (defined as > 20 ng/mL) in 27.7% of RA patients who were vitamin D-deficient, although duration of therapy was not reported. This suggests that different levels of vitamin D replacement may be required in different RA patients, depending on pre-supplementation of vitamin D levels, sunlight exposure and skin colour (darker skin absorbs less UV light to make vitamin D). Failure to adequately replete RA patients could also be related to poor treatment compliance or inadequate duration of supplementation. Importantly, inadequate repletion was related to higher HAQ scores for RA patients, implying that inadequate improvement of vitamin D status following supplementation had poorer outcomes. Alternatively higher disease activity may simply be associated with less time spent outdoors, indirectly impacting sunlight exposure and skin synthesis of vitamin D. Further RCTs are needed to more clearly define the optimal levels of vitamin D for patients with RA, and how to achieve and maintain these levels. The next section of the review describes the reported supplementation trials for vitamin D and RA.

Disease duration and severity, concomitant medication regimen, type of/duration of supplementation regimen, number of outcomes and period over which these outcomes were measured. A recent meta-analysis identified 9 RCTs of vitamin D supplementation for ≥ 3 months in rheumatic diseases, including 5 studies of RA patients. In RA, there was a decrease in the rate of disease flare, VAS and DAS-28 with vitamin D supplementation; however, all failed to reach statistical significance. Similar findings have also been reported in previous meta-analyses on this subject. Conversely, a meta-analysis conducted in 2012 found that all but one of the 11 studies included in the meta-analysis suggested low vitamin D intake was linked with both increased risk of RA and greater disease activity; however, the studies included in that analysis were cohort/association by design, and not RCTs. Challenges associated with identifying whether vitamin D supplementation has a beneficial effect in RCTs to date include inter-study heterogeneity and relatively small sample numbers for a meta-analysis, with only 5 RCTs included, thus emphasising the need for larger RCTs in different subsets of RA patients to fully elucidate the role, if any, for vitamin D supplementation in the management of RA. In addition, there may be differences in vitamin D-binding protein levels, and other genetic

variants, which influence the efficacy of vitamin D supplementation. Vitamin D supplementation in low/moderate doses is not thought to be harmful to patients, has wider health benefits, is relatively inexpensive and has fewer side effects/interactions compared with many other commonly used treatments for RA, such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), or conventional synthetic or biological disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs). Evidence is also emerging that vitamin D may augment certain therapies in RA. In one in vitro study, vitamin D 1,25-(OH)₂D₃ was shown to act synergistically with the biologic drug abatacept to inhibit T cell activation driven by anti-CD3 cross-linking, and promote a pro-regulatory CD28 phenotype. The potential for enhancing the effects of biologics with simple, low-risk addition of 1,25-(OH)₂D₃ is interesting, and further work is required to validate this initial in vitro finding.

Conclusions

Future studies of vitamin D and RA are needed firstly to expand our current understanding of the mechanisms by which 1,25-(OH)₂D₃ is able to regulate key cells associated with RA. In particular, the observation that T cells from the inflamed joints of RA patients are insensitive to 1,25-(OH)₂D₃ indicates that RA disease is associated with a corruption of vitamin D signalling that may be fundamentally important for RA disease pathology, and the therapeutic use of vitamin D. A key question that remains to be answered is whether vitamin D has greater benefits in protecting against the onset of RA as opposed to its potential application as a therapy for established RA disease. Thus, future studies to assess the effects of vitamin D supplementation on disease prevention in individuals at risk of RA, and disease development in those at early stages of RA, are required. These studies are likely to be informed by recent meta-analyses for immune effects of vitamin D. Notably, the observation from the analysis of acute respiratory infection trials that vitamin D supplementation was more beneficial in patients with low baseline serum vitamin D, and was more effective when supplementation was used as lower daily or weekly dosing, provides some important pointers for future studies of vitamin D and RA. Future studies also need to take into consideration clinical subgroups of patients, including distinguishing between ethnic groups and disease of different

durations. The potential for a simple, low-risk and low-cost intervention such as vitamin D as a plausible adjunctive treatment for RA is an exciting notion. Robust evidence to support wider routine use of vitamin D supplementation in RA has the potential to significantly enhance treatment for RA and other autoimmune diseases.

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